

Vascular Malformation, Arterio-Venous Malformation: Early Pregnancy and Post-Partum Manifestation

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ABSTRACT

Arterio-venous malformation (AVM) are rare entities that can be potentially life threatening if left untreated due to massive blood loss during or after uterine manipulation. AVM are characterized by an abnormal leash of vessels allowing for arterio-venous shunting. They can occur anywhere in the body but are most common in brain [1]. There is direct arteriovenous communication with no intervening capillary bed. They can be congenital [2] or acquired [3]. They can occur anywhere in the body but have unique clinical presentation when affecting the female pelvis. Enhanced myometrial vascularity (EMV), often misdiagnosed as an acquired uterine arteriovenous malformation, is the presence of transiently increased blood flow within the uterine myometrium, typically associated with complications of pregnancy.

Herein, we report the two rare cases of young women with a vascular lesion of uterus successfully treated with uterine artery embolization. We will review the relevant literature, clinical course, diagnostic studies, focusing on the best options for treatment and investigation modalities.

Keywords: Arterio- venous malformation (AVM); Uterine artery embolization; Myometrial enhanced vascularity; DSA; Distal subtraction angiography

CASE REPORT

In November 2021, a 36 years old, Asian woman, G4Para 1+2 presented to emergency department for delivery in tertiary care centre. She reported having reduced foetal movements associated with abdominal discomfort at 36

weeks 5 days gestation. History signifies one Caesarean section and 2 consecutive miscarriages first and second trimester. Both did not require surgical evacuation. Pertaining to past medical condition of deep venous thrombosis and pulmonary embolism in 2016, multidisciplinary team was involved and she continued low molecular weight heparin during stay in hospital. Her obstetric course in index pregnancy was uneventful including foetal screening and growth. Moreover, her echocardiography and bilateral lower limb compression doppler were normal. She was discharged on rivaroxaban 15mg/12 hours for 3weeks after uneventful caesarean section at 37 weeks 2 days of gestation with clear follow up plan with obstetric and pulmonology outpatient. Operative findings include omental adhesions and fibroses abdominal wall. Uterine anatomy and endometrial cavity were found normal. She presented to emergency department at 16th day of caesarean section with heavy vaginal bleeding, looked pale, however hemodynamically stable with involuted uterus and closed cervical os with active fresh bleeding of moderate amount. Haemoglobin was found 10.5 gm. Transabdominal and vaginal ultrasound revealed posterior uterine wall lesion suggestive of arteriovenous malformation with empty endometrial cavity. (Image C). CT Angioplasty was evident of contrast blush within the anterior myometrial wall persistent on arterial and venous phases as described likely representing arterio-venous malformation (AVM). Portal vein appears attenuated with multiple collateral vessels and cavernoma along with splenomegaly, findings suggestive of portal hypertension.

She subsequently undergone bilateral uterine artery embolization, aortoiliac angiography showed enlarged right uterine artery with abnormal enhancement at the dome of the uterus mainly supplied by the right uterine artery. no Arteriovenous fistula or malformation noted.

She received packed cells and rivaroxaban replaced to Enoxaparin. She successfully followed up in vascular and obstetric clinic with advice of effective contraception.

Second case with similarities of ethnicity and age group. Her obstetric history include para 6 with 4 caesarean sections and 1 partial molar pregnancy. In 2021, July she presented to emergency department with mild vaginal bleeding. Clinical condition was stable and ultrasound was suggestive of blighted ovum at 14 weeks of gestation. She with managed with two cycles of misoprostol without any sign of expulsion with tightly closed cervical os. She was offered a third cycle with a gap of a week which she could not attend and lost the follow up with us. 12 weeks after, she presented to ED with vaginal bleeding. Abdominal examination revealed soft, non-tender abdomen and vaginal examination signifies a bulky uterus with closed cervical os and mild vaginal bleeding. Transabdominal and transvaginal in early pregnancy assessment unit revealed irregular endometrium with mixed echogenicity starting from uterine fundus till internal cervical Os (image B). Endometrial thickness at fundal area was 9 mm and lower part of uterus was around 19mm. There was a marked increased vascularity in the anterior part of the uterus with impression of retained products of conception or suspected AV malformation.

CT Angiogram of the pelvis revealed Uterine arterio-venous malformation (probably acquired) Right ovarian simple cyst (image D). MRI of the pelvis revealed Tangled intra cavitory uterine small vessels and congested uterine vascular arcade, that may raise the possibility of an acquired AVM.(image A). She subsequently undergone Uterine Artery Embolization 14 weeks after first presentation to ER as a missed miscarriage. Which

again signifies the challenges of intensive investigations and lack of follow up by patient due to lengthy management and indefinite initial diagnosis.

Right uterine artery angiography showed abnormal enhancing lesion from right and left side of the pelvis with patent communication with the right ovarian artery.

Left internal iliac angiography showed aneurysmal dilatation related to the anterior division trunk with abnormal enhancing lesion in the left side of the pelvis supplied by the left uterine artery. left uterine artery angiography showed large abnormal enhancing lesion on the left side of the pelvis with minimal supply to the right side. no communication was noted with the left ovarian artery. Patient discharged in stable condition and followed with vascular and gynae unit with successful outcome-

Both of our patients preferred to conserve the uterus unless facing life threatening situation.

Image A: MRI Case one: T1 shows the intrauterine mixed signals predominantly high in T1 presenting hematoma.

Image B: Case 2 ultrasound: Distended endometrial cavity with soft tissues mixed echogenicity contents. Doppler US shows multiple dilated tortuous vessels at the anterior myometrial wall.

Image C: Case 1, ultrasound image with focal myometrial vascularity on doppler.

Image D: Computer topography with contrast, case 2: Dilated tortious vessels at anterior mid and lower part of the myometrium intensely enhancing in the arterial phase, with early venous drainage to common iliac veins in the arterial phase.it extends o distended endometrial cavity.

DISCUSSION

AVM are characterized by an abnormal leash of vessels allowing for arterio-venous shunting. They can occur anywhere in the body but are most common in brain ^[1].

Acquired case largely related to iatrogenic event extended to but not limited to Cesarean section, myomectomies, repair of congenital uterine malformation or surgical management of miscarriages involving extensive curettage ^[4,5]. Congenital AVMs are the result of abnormal development of primitive vessels that result in connections between pelvic arteries and veins in the uterus without an interconnecting capillary bed. Ultrasonography, Computer tomography and magnetic resonance imaging are the main investigating modalities which can confirm and guide us about treating uterine vascular abnormalities.

In an AVM, blood passes quickly from an artery to a vein, disrupting the usual blood flow and depriving the surrounding tissues. Symptoms vary depending on location and amount of blood loss. Capillaries are physiological unit of normal perfusion, In AVM, this tiny unit disrupts and perfusion process is being compromised to the surrounding tissue- These tangled blood vessels are malformed, can weaken and rupture causing subsequent life-threatening bleeding. Vascular malformation can be classified according to location or primarily to their flow characteristic. Slow flow (lymphatic and venous) or fast flow (arteriovenous). Slow flow malformation is often treated with sclerotherapy while arterio- venous fast flow malformed vessels usually require embolization. They can occur anywhere in the body but have unique clinical presentation when affecting the female pelvis. Following are the possible sites for these complex lesions, classifies as Location specific, Subtypes

- 1- Cerebral arteriovenous malformation (Spetzler AVM grading system) ^[6]
- 2- Hepatic arteriovenous malformation
- 3- Musculoskeletal arteriovenous malformation
- 4- Pulmonary arteriovenous malformation
- 5- Renal arteriovenous malformation
- 6- Uterine arteriovenous malformation

Diagnosis and treatment are challenging endeavor for both physician and patient. There is interchangeably used term in past called “enhanced myometrial vascularity” ^[7,8] which is a sonographic appearance of hypervascularity lesion within the uterine myometrium that demonstrates turbulent flow and considered as separate entities. In 2015, Annual World Congress of the international Society of Ultrasound in Obstetrics and Gynecology (ISUOG) , it was recommended that “enhanced myometrial vascularity” is the preferred term for what was previously known as an “acquired uterine arteriovenous malformation. The recommendation was made because most of the cases do not represent a true or typical feature of arterio-venous malformation. ^[9]

Considering epidemiological pattern and distribution, uterine arterio-venous malformations are almost entirely related to acquired type malformations secondary to multiple pregnancies, miscarriages, previous uterine surgeries, termination of pregnancies etc.

Our both cases were related to pregnancies and likely acquired malformation. First case was a post cesarean presented as bleeding 2 weeks after the birth, all her presentation and images were highly suggestive of acquired arteriovenous malformation, angiography revealed an enlarged right uterine artery with abnormal enhancement at the dome of the uterus mainly supplied by the right uterine artery, no definite arteriovenous fistula or malformation noted. Which is again a non-typical form of previously reported in literature an enhanced myometrial vascularity. Hence, we conclude that the typical presentation of vaginal bleeding after pregnancy event which was highly suspected AV malformation on standard radiology investigations can be seen as enhanced abnormal myometrial vascularity. Irrespective of angiographic findings, clinical presentation was similar to secondary postpartum haemorrhage and radiological investigations supported and guided the management. Also, this woman has undergone only one uterine surgery which was caesarean section which again suggest a disproportionate risk of high morbid conditions irrespective of number of scars in the uterus. Second case was proved as AV malformation on radiology investigations and angiogram. This was a prolonged missed miscarriage complicated with intermittent spotting and bleeding and this uterus was screeled 4 times in past pregnancies in addition to one molar pregnancy. Delay in diagnosis and loss of follow up is potentially possible both from the health care team and patient. It was a challenging case, at beginning she was offered multiple cycles of misoprostol without success. This failure of treatment had guided us for further intensive investigations which the patient could not compliant expectedly. However, despite prolonged loss of follow up she was appropriately treated and managed according to standard treatment. This case signifies the strong relation to higher order uterine scars and possible vascular malformation. In conclusion of both cases, any classic presentation can be a consequence of underlying serious pathology, differential diagnosis should be in mind before counselling the patients if initial treatment is not responded. Both cases managed well with uterine artery embolization which is not a new modality and considered as lifesaving procedure in uterine vascular defects.

Clinical Presentation

Irrespective of sonological or further advanced radiological diagnosis of enhanced lesion or AV malformation, clinical presentation shares the same course and symptoms. It varies from being asymptomatic to intermittent or constant heavy vaginal bleeding with subsequent anemia symptoms. It may be massive and life-threatening in young women or a woman with reproductive age group. Pertaining to clinical presentation in our case, history of recent pregnancy is typical. As these malformations are less common after menopause, post-menopausal bleeding is rarely seen.

Differential Diagnosis

Sonographic appearance of a hyper vascular lesion within the uterine myometrium with turbulent flow suspects a following diagnosis:

- True uterine AV malformation: rare and shows early venous filling on DSA

- Retained products of conception: Differentiation is often difficult, shows thickened endometrium without myometrial involvement
- GSD, gestational trophoblastic disease: markedly high BHCG with enlarged uterus and centrally located lesion
- Endometrial polypoid growth or endometritis

Pathology

AVM are characterized by an abnormal mesh of vessels allowing for arterio-venous shunting. They can occur anywhere in the body but are most common in brain ^[1].

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Congenital uterine arteriovenous malformations tend to have multiple feeding arteries, a central nidus (a tangle of vessels with histologic characteristics of both arteries and veins), and numerous large draining veins ^[10]. Acquired or traumatic uterine arteriovenous malformations (also called arteriovenous fistulas) represent multiple small arteriovenous fistulas between intramural arterial branches and the myometrial venous plexus ^[11] They typically represent a single artery joining a simple vein.

Investigational Modalities

Ultrasound

Ultrasound is a first possible investigation which is easily available, acceptable by patient and cost effective. Despite having advancement, accuracy and technical efficacy still it is not possible to differentiate enhanced myometrial vascularity from a true AV malformation. ^[12]

On greyscale ultrasound, anechoic, tortuous structure within the uterine cavity is suggestive of retained products of conception. Malformed vessels on color Doppler ultrasound, appears as mosaic turbulent pattern with multiple flow reversals. This demonstrates low impedance flow with a high peak systolic velocity (PSV) ≥ 20 cm/s and low arterial waveform pulsatility. It should be noted that while some authors consider a PSV >60 cm/s to be high risk. ^[13,14]

Magnetic resonance Imaging MRI

For all woman presenting as abnormal vaginal bleeding with suspected sonological features of vascular lesions should offered an MRI. shows multiple serpentine flow-related signal voids typically seen in the uterine wall, endometrial cavity, and parametrium on T1 and T2 weighted images. Contrast-enhanced dynamic MR angiography can depict complex serpentine abnormal vessels that enhance as intensely as normal vessels and show early venous return ^[15]

Angiography: Distal subtraction angiography

Digital subtraction angiography (DSA) shows a hyper vascular lesion *without* early venous filling. Conversely, a true uterine arteriovenous malformation will show a hyper vascular mass *with* early venous filling ^[16.17]

Treatment modalities

As this is clear form above discussion that presentation varies from asymptomatic findings to devastating life threatening bleeding. So, treatment should be individualized and depends on presentation and possible risk of bleeding in future. Traditionally, hysterectomy or uterine arteries ligation were the treatment modalities for cases of uterine AVMs. Angiographic arterial embolization has recently become the preferred management protocol because it is minimally invasive and has the potential to preserve fertility. Several authors have described the regression of AVM with conservative therapy or spontaneous resolution ^[19].

Similarly, cases with highly suspected enhanced vascular lesions with retained products can be safely offered dilatation and evacuation with all safety measure with anticipation of heavy bleeding. Risk of hemorrhage is comparable to the cases without enhanced myometrial vascularity except in cases of scar pregnancy or molar pregnancy^[18]. In the setting of significant or prolonged vaginal bleeding, radiologically-guided uterine artery embolization is warranted, followed by more invasive surgical management (typically hysteroscopic electrosurgery, uterine/internal iliac artery ligation, or hysterectomy) as a lifesaving procedure.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion of both cases, clinical suspicion should be raised for any young woman presenting with abnormal vaginal bleeding after recent pregnancy event or in current early pregnancy and who are not responding to expectant management. These typical presentations may be a consequence of a simple prolonged missed miscarriage to serious underlying pathology. Differential diagnosis should be in mind before counselling the patients if initial treatment is not responded. Ultrasound is an initial investigation tool which suspect and guide us for further imaging techniques. Also, role of multidisciplinary team, appropriate counselling for invasive treatment are the cornerstone which can save the young woman life and conserve the uterus. Both of our cases managed well with uterine artery embolization which is not a new modality and considered as gold standard lifesaving procedure in uterine vascular defects. ^[19]

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